

A Study on Institutional Supports of Entrepreneurship Development in Karnataka State

Dr.N.Honnurwamy

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Vijayanagara Sri Krishnadevaraya University,
Post Graduate Centre-Nandihalli,Sandur-583119

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10082700>

Published Date: 08-November-2023

Abstract: The institutional support system for entrepreneurship development in India has been designed at four levels, viz., (i) Central Government, (ii) State Government, (iii) Non-Government Support System, and (iv) District Industries Centers. This paper is going to attempt on history of Entrepreneurship in Karnataka and what are the factors mainly effect on entrepreneurship development, functions, process and how that financial institutions and training institutions empower the productivity of entrepreneurs and their abilities, this research work mainly summarize the process of institutional support to entrepreneurship’.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Training, Empowerment, Financing, Industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship can be described as a process of action an entrepreneur. Undertakes to establish his enterprise. Entrepreneurship is a creative activity. It is the ability to create and build something from practically nothing. It is a knack of sensing opportunity where others see chaos, contradiction and confusion. Entrepreneurship is the attitude of Mind to seek opportunities, take calculated risks and derive benefits by setting up a venture. It comprises of numerous activities involved in conception, creation and running an enterprise.

The role of entrepreneurship institution support financial and training institution entrepreneurs occupy important positions. On the industrial economics of the country basic of low investment detriment height potentially for gainfully employment generation and winder disporsanal of industries.

The economic development of advance of the world has been attributed to the growth of entrepreneurs. They are so many institutions and organization which is involved in entrepreneurship development actives and there are people who join this the growing need of industries by supply traditional managers / corporate managers.

In the era of liberalization, privatization and globalization along with ongoing IT revolution, capable entrepreneurs are making use of the opportunities emerging from the evolving scenario. However, a large segment of the population, particularly in the industrially backward regions/rural areas generally lags behind in taking advantage of these opportunities. Therefore, there is a need to provide skill development and entrepreneurship development training to such people in order to mainstream them in the ongoing process of economic growth.

Entrepreneurship development and training is, thus, one of the key elements for development of micro and small enterprises (MSEs), particularly, the first generation entrepreneurs. To undertake this task on regular basis, the Ministry has set up three national-level Entrepreneurship Development Institutes (EDIs). These are the National Institute for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (NI-MSME), Hyderabad; The Indian Institute of Entrepreneurship (IIE), Guwahati and the National

Institute for Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development (NIESBUD), Noida. Further, the Ministry has been implementing (in addition to the schemes of MSME-DO) an important scheme, namely,

Therefore, most governments in the world strive to augment supply of competent and globally competitive entrepreneurs in their respective countries. While developed nations have a reasonably good pace of entrepreneurial supply, most developing countries suffer from dearth of such entrepreneurs. This is one of the reasons for the poverty in developing countries, despite their rich resource endowments.

Financial schemes for women entrepreneurship: With a view that women entrepreneurs should come forward in industrial field and become self-sufficient, governmental and financial institutions have announced many schemes of providing financial assistance. Seed Capital Scheme- In order to start one's own business this scheme is undertaken by the government. Mohanty (2004) suggested that various self-employment and income generating schemes such as IRDP, SEEDY, PMRY, SSI, KVI and DWCR implemented in Orissa have made significant contribution towards economic empowerment and self-employment of women and development of women entrepreneurship.

✚ History of entrepreneurship institution in Karnataka:-

The history of entrepreneurship is important walkway. Even in India. In the pre-colonial times the Indian trade and business was at peak. India was experts in smelting of metal such as brass and tin. "Kanishk Empire" in the 1st century stated nurturing. India entrepreneurship and traders.

Entrepreneurship instructions are the result of their dimensions working together: conducive. Former conditions well-designed govt. programs and supportive cultural attitudes. Accrues their perspective of entrepreneurs'. Two major conclusions are apparent; firstly economic psychological and sociological Academic fields accept that entrepreneurship is a process. Entrepreneurship is clearly more than an economic function

1.1 Basic theoretical concept & contents of the topic:-

The entrepreneurship was first established. In the 1700 and the mining has evolved. The entrepreneurship is very an old concept according to which anyone who runs business is called an entrepreneur.

Economic growth hinges upon entrepreneurship. A vibrant entrepreneurial climate. Provides new jobs. Increase assess competitive and produces novel goods and services. The economic development of advanced country of the world has been attributed to the growth of entrepreneurs.

The theoretical debate whether entrepreneurs can be created through training and finance intervention has not arrived at any definitive conclusion. While some scholars hold the view that training is an effective intervention in developing latent entrepreneurial traits,

There are others who hold the view that these traits grow into enterprise creation only under a conducive environment. Another set of scholars explain entrepreneurship as the result of the interaction the individual, organizational, procedural and environmental factors. It therefore follows that by identifying individuals with latent entrepreneurial traits and making the environment more conducive, it is possible to 'create' entrepreneurs.

This kind of intervention assumes added importance in the context of developing countries which are acutely deficient in entrepreneurial resources training and financial. Policy makers in both developed and developing nations now pay considerable attention in creating entrepreneurs through various forms of interventions.

Some Facts about Entrepreneurs and Entrepreneurship:

E:xamine needs, wants, and problems to see how they can improve the way needs and wants are Problems overcome.

N:arrow the possible opportunities to one specific "best" opportunity.

T:hink of innovative ideas and narrow them to the "best" idea. Einstein College of Engineering.

R:esearch the opportunity and idea thoroughly.

E:nlist the best sources of advice and assistance that they can find.

P: lane their ventures and look for possible problems that might arise.

R: ank the risks and the possible rewards.

E: valuate the risks and possible rewards and make their decision to act or not to act.

N: ever hang on to an idea, no matter how much they may love it, if research shows it Won't work.

E: mploy the resources necessary for the venture to succeed.

U: nderstand that they will have to work long and hard to make their ventures succeed.

R: ealize a sense of accomplishment from their successful ventures and learn from their failures to help them achieve success in the future.

🌟 Definition of entrepreneurship development: -

➤ **Adam smith (1776)** “define and entrepreneurship who forms an organization for individual purpose – who is a capita. An effort is made illustrate the real life situation of respondents in their business ventures which reflect women entrepreneurs”.

“Entrepreneur is an employer, master, merchant but explicitly considered as a capitalist”

➤ **Oxford Dictionary:** - “A person who sets up a business or businesses, taking on financial risks in the hope of profit”

➤ **According to A Schumpeter:** - “The entrepreneurship is essentially a creative activity or it is an innovative function”.

🌟 Entrepreneurship

- A theory of evolution of economic activities.
- A continuous process of economic development.
- An ingredient to economic development.
- Essentially a creative activity or an innovative function.
- A risk taking factor which is responsible for an end result.
- Usually understood with reference to individual business.
- The name given to the factor of production, which performs the functions of enterprise.
- Creates awareness among people about economic activity.
- Generates Self-employment and additional employment

🌟 Concept of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a multi-dimensional task defined differently by different authorities. Centillion was the first to use the term ‘entrepreneur’. He portrayed an entrepreneur as one discharging the function of direction and speculation. According to J.B Say, an entrepreneur is to combine the factors of production into a producing organism.

Characteristics of Entrepreneurship:

✚ Role of entrepreneurship:-

- Create opportunities -Job creation, careers, and new products/services
- Economic growth, productivity improvement, and innovation.
- Poverty alleviation and social opportunities.
- Create new customers and open up new markets.

✚ Qualities of a successful entrepreneur

Let us now think about the qualities of a successful entrepreneur. There may be many qualities. Needed to successfully run an enterprise. However, the following qualities are considered important.

(I) Initiative: In the world of business, opportunities come and go. An entrepreneur has to be a man of action. He should be able to initiate action and take advantage of opportunity. Once you miss the opportunity it will not come again. Therefore, initiative on the part of entrepreneur is a must.

(ii) Willingness to assume risk: In any business there is an element of risk. It implies that a businessman may be successful or unsuccessful. In other words it is not necessary that every business shall earn profit. This deters individuals to take up business. However, an entrepreneur always volunteers to take risks to run a business and be successful. **(iii) Ability to learn from experience** An entrepreneur may commit mistakes. However, once an error is committed, it should not be repeated as that will lead to heavy losses. So, one should learn from his mistakes. An entrepreneur, therefore, should have the ability to learn from experience.

(iv) Motivation: Motivation is key to success. This is necessary for success in every walk of life. Once you get motivated to do something you will not rest unless you complete it. For example, sometimes you become so much interested in reading a story or a novel that you do not sleep unless you complete it. This kind of interest in the work comes through motivation. This is an essential quality of a successful entrepreneur.

(v) Self-confidence For achieving success in life, one should have confidence in himself or herself. A person who lacks confidence can neither do any work himself nor can inspire others to work. Self confidence is reflected in courage, enthusiasm and the ability to lead. A successful entrepreneur must have self-confidence.

(vi) Orientation towards hard work: There is no substitute for hard work in life. While running a business, everyday, one problem or the other may arise. The businessman has to be vigilant about it and solve it as early as possible. This requires hard work on the part of entrepreneur. He cannot afford to say that now office time is over and I will not work. In some situations he may even have to work for the whole night. Thus, orientation towards hard work is the secret of success of an entrepreneur.

(vi) Decision making ability: In running an enterprise, the entrepreneur has to take a number of decisions. He should Entrepreneurship 195 therefore be capable of taking suitable and timely decision. In other words he must take right decision at the right time. In the present world things move very fast. If an entrepreneur does not have the ability to take timely decision, he might miss opportunity and incur loss.

✚ Functions' of an entrepreneur

An entrepreneur frequently has to wear many hats. He has to perceive opportunity, plan, organize resources, and oversee production, marketing, and liaison with officials. Most importantly he has to innovate and bear risk. The main functions of an entrepreneur are as follows:

1. Innovation:Innovation is one of the most important functions of an Entrepreneur according to Schumpeter. An entrepreneur uses information, knowledge and intuition to come up with new products, new methods of reducing costs of a product, improvement in design or function of a product, discovering new markets or new ways of organization of industry. Through innovation, an entrepreneur converts a material into a resource or combines existing resources into new and more productive configurations.

2. Risk and uncertainty bearing:According to Homeliest an entrepreneur performs the function of risk and uncertainty bearing. Every decision pertaining to development of new products, adapting new technologies, opening up new markets involves risk. Decision-making in an environment of uncertainty requires anticipation of risk. Profit is said to be the reward for anticipating and taking such risks. An entrepreneur develops the art of decision-making under conditions of uncertainty as a matter of survival.

3. Organization building:An entrepreneur has to organize men, material and other resources. He has to perform the functions of planning, co-ordination and control. He has to use his leadership qualities to build a team, generate resources and solve problems. With his organizational skills an entrepreneur builds an enterprise from scratch, nurtures it and makes it grow. His vision sows the seeds for a sound and vibrant organization and synergies are built in the enterprise.

Entrepreneurship
Own Boss
Make own plans
Creative activity
Can be negative sometimes,
generally surplus
Creates Wealth, contributes to GDP
Can choose from- Industry
Trade or Service Enterprise

www.smallindustryindia.com

Difference between entrepreneur and entrepreneurship

The term entrepreneur is used to describe men and women who establish and manage their own business. The process involved is called entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is an abstraction whereas entrepreneurs are tangible people. Entrepreneurship is a process and an entrepreneur is a person. Entrepreneurship is the outcome of complex socio-economic, psychological and other factors.

Entrepreneur is the key individual central to entrepreneurship who makes things happen. Entrepreneur is the actor, entrepreneurship is the act. Entrepreneurship is the most effective way of bridging the gap between science and the market place by creating new enterprises. An entrepreneur is the catalyst who brings about this change.

Financing Entrepreneurship

In the social scientific literature, entrepreneurial finance is practically synonymous with the study of venture capital firms. Venture capital, the reasoning goes, occupies a unique place in the financial system by specializing in relatively risky long-term financing of entrepreneurs with little in the way of assets to collateralize. Most entrepreneurial firms

With high growth potential need external financing, but few intermediaries and individuals are in a position to extend such financing given the significant problems inherent in monitoring investments in new firms with no track record and tremendous uncertainties. VCs place themselves in a unique position to make such investments in two ways. First, they specialize in effectively understanding and monitoring such new firms and their managers in ways that reduce the chances of opportunistic behavior by entrepreneurs. And second, they transfer a critical bundle of knowledge, skills, and contacts to entrepreneurial.

Firms that reduce the uncertainties it faces and increases the likelihood of success

1.4.2) Entrepreneurs main problems are.....,

- Financial supports.
- Training supports.

Today present financial situation is the very essential and important, because entrepreneurs requirements more than financial problems supportive training problems. Comparative to the other nations entrepreneur investor or capitalists is contributes. Because lack of the technological institutions. And business back bone of the financial supports. Scheme for Assistance for Strengthening of Training Infrastructure of Existing and New Entrepreneurship Development Institutes (EDIs).

The main objectives of the scheme are

- promoting entrepreneurship for creating self-employment through enterprise creation;
- facilitating creation of training infrastructure; and
- Supporting research on entrepreneurship related issues.

1.4.3 at same additional main problem entrepreneurial

- Location / land problems
- Government taxation problems
- Technical skill people require
- Technological problems
- Computation problem
- Marketing problems
- Scarcity of the bank lone

1.4.4 Problems Faced By the Entrepreneur's:-

Entrepreneurs faced many problems to get ahead in their life and in their business. They are as follows.

- Lack of family support,
- Lack of finance,
- Lack of confidence and faith
- Lack of right policies,
- Social issues,
- Market problems,
- Occupation mobility
- Lack of Government support
- Production and personal problems etc.

🚩 Bank of India is operating following schemes for entrepreneurship development in the country.

- Star artisan credit card scheme.
- Small entrepreneur credit card scheme.
- Star SSI supreme scheme.
- Small entrepreneur trade card scheme.
- Star self-employment credit card scheme.

2. ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

The industrial health of a society depends on the level of entrepreneurship existing in it. A country might remain backward not because of lack of natural resources or dearth of capital [as it is many times believed] but because of lack of entrepreneurial talents or its inability to tap the latent entrepreneurial talents existing in that society. Entrepreneurs historically have altered the direction of National economies, industry or markets- Japan, Singapore, Korea,

1.1. B) Baumol's Sales or Revenue Maximization Theory:

Assumptions, Explanation and Criticisms

Prof Baumol on the theory of Oligopoly presented a managerial theory of the firm based on the sales maximization.

Assumptions:

The theory is based on the following assumptions:

1. There is a single period time horizon of the firm.
2. The firm aims at maximizing its total sales revenue in the long run subject to a profit constraint.
3. The firm's minimum profit constraint is set competitively in terms of the current market value of its shares.
4. The firm is oligopolistic whose cost curves are U-shaped and the demand curve is downward sloping. Its total cost and revenue curves are also of the conventional type.

Explanation:

Baumol's findings of oligopoly firms in America reveal that they follow the sales maximization objective. According to Baumol, with the separation of ownership and control in modern corporations, managers seek prestige and higher salaries by trying to expand company sales even at the expense of profits.

Being a consultant to a number of firms, Baumol observes that when asked how their business went last year, the business managers often responded, "our sales were up to three million dollars." Thus, according to Baumol, revenue or sales maximization rather than profit maximization is consistent with the actual behavior of firms.

1. Baumol cites evidence to suggest that short-run revenue maximization may be consistent with long-run profit maximization. But sales maximization is regarded as the short-run and long-run goal of the management. Sales maximization is not only a means but an end in itself. He gives a number of arguments in support of his theory.
2. A firm attaches great importance to the magnitude of sales and is much concerned about declining sales.
3. If the sales of a firm are declining, banks, creditors and the capital market are not prepared to provide finance to it.
4. Its own distributors and dealers might stop taking interest in it.
5. Consumers might not buy its product because of its unpopularity.
6. Firm reduces its managerial and other staff with fall in sales.
7. If firm's sales are large, there are economies of scale, the firm expands and earns large profits.
8. Salaries of workers and management also depend to a large extent on more sales and the firm gives them bonus and other facilities.

By sales maximization, Baumol means maximization of total revenue. It does not imply the sale of large quantities of output, but refers to the increase in money sales (in rupee, dollar, etc.). Sales can increase up to the point of profit maximization where the marginal cost equals marginal revenue. If sales are increased beyond this point, money sales may increase at the expense of profits. But the oligopolistic firm wants its money sales to grow even though it earns minimum profits.

Minimum profits refer to the amount which is less than maximum profits. The minimum profits are determined on the basis of firm's need to maximize sales and also to sustain growth of sales. Minimum profits are required either in the form of retained earnings or new capital from the market.

The firm also needs minimum profits to finance future sales. Further, they are essential for a firm for paying dividends on share capital and for meeting other financial requirements. Thus minimum profits serve as a constraint on the

maximization of a firm's revenue. "Maximum revenue will be obtained only", according to Baumol, "at an output at which the elasticity of demand is unity, i.e., at which marginal revenue is zero. This is the condition which replaces the "marginal cost equals marginal revenue profit maximization rule."

Baumol's model is illustrated in Figure 5 where TC is the total cost curve, TR the total revenue curve, TP the total profit curve and MP the minimum profit or profit constraint line. The firm maximizes its profits at OQ level of output corresponding to the highest point B on the TP curve. But the aim of the firm is to maximize its sales rather than profits.

Its sales maximization output is OK where the total revenue KL is the maximum at the highest point of TR. This sales maximization output OK is higher than the profit maximization output OQ. But sales maximization is subject to minimum profit constraint. Suppose the minimum profit level of the firm is represented by the line MP.

The output OK will not maximize sales as the minimum profits OM are not being covered by total profits KS. For sales maximization, the firm should produce that level of output which not only covers the minimum profits but also gives the highest total revenue consistent with it. This level is represented by OD level of output where the minimum profits DC (=OM) are consistent with DE amount of total revenue at the price DE/OD, (i.e., total revenue/total output).

Baumol's model of sales maximization points out that the profit maximization output will be smaller than the sales-maximization output OD, and price higher than under sales maximization. The reason for a lower price under sales maximization is that both total revenue and total output are equally higher while. Under profit maximization, total output is much less as compared to total revenue. Imagine if QB is joined to TR in Figure 5. "If at the point of maximum profit" writes Baumol, "the firm earns more profit than the required minimum, it will pay the sales maximizes to lower his price and increase his physical output."

Conclusion

This theory leads to the conclusion that a sales-revenue maximization firm:

- (a) Will produce at a higher level,
- (b) Will keep low prices, and
- (c) Will invest in such a manner, as on advertisement, that the demand for its product will increase.

Implications (or Superiority) of the Theory:

Baumol's sales maximization theory has some important implications which make it superior to the profit maximization model of the firm.

1. The sales maximizing firm prefers larger sales to profits. Since it maximizes its revenue when MR is zero, it will charge lower prices than that charged by the profit maximizing firm.

2. It follows from the above that the sales maximizing output will be larger than the profit maximizing output.
3. The sales maximiser would spend more on advertising in order to earn larger revenue than the profit maximiser subject to the minimum profit constraint.

Criticisms:

Baumol's sales maximization model is not free from certain weaknesses.

3. Hawkins has also shown that Baumol's conclusion that a sales-maximiser will in general produce and advertise more than a profit-maximiser, is invalid. According to Hawkins, a sales-maximiser "may choose a higher, lower or identical output—and a higher, lower or identical advertising budget. It depends on the responsiveness of demand to advertising rather than price cuts. This conclusion holds for firms producing only one product, or one group of products."
4. In the case of multiproduct, Baumol has argued that revenue and profit maximization yield the same results. But Williamson has shown that sales maximization yields different results from profit maximization.
5. Another weakness of this model is that it ignores the interdependence of the prices of oligopolistic firms.
6. The model fails to explain "observed market situations in which price are kept for considerable time periods in the range of inelastic demand."
7. The model ignores not only actual competition, but also the threat of potential competition from rival oligopolistic firms.
8. The model does not show how equilibrium in an industry, in which all firms are sales maximizes, will be attained. Baumol does not establish the relationship between the firm and industry.
9. Prof. Hall in his analysis of 500 firms came to the conclusion that firms do not operate in accordance with the objective of sales maximization.

Despite these criticisms, there is no denying the fact that sales maximization forms an important goal of firms in the present day business world.

3. RESEARESH DESIGEN AND METHODOLOGY

The present study undertaken by the Karnataka state as a secondary data from selected form the Karnataka all district. Of the entrepreneurship instructions supports of training and financial supports. The present study Karnataka entrepreneurship financial supports and development in entrepreneur.

Sampling design: - is a pearly based on secondary data.

Sources and methods of the data collected the study usage secondary:-

Secondary data it's collected from the government publication books, internet, library & magazines, the data collected from secondary data analysis the carefully sampling average & percentage techniques are use to summers. The data finding of the study are presented which the help of tables and graphs, in present study the entrepreneurship development instructions on financial and training development this study has been determined by development.

Methods of data analysis and techniques:-

The data collected from the secondary data analysis carefully. Sampling average and percentage techniques are use to summers data. Findings of the study are presented with the help of tables and graphs. In the present study the entrepreneurship development institutions in the study has been determined by the development.

The study utilizes various samples statistics. Statistical tool with are as follows.

- Graphs
 - Line bar graphs
 - Bar graphs
- Pie charts
- Percentage charts
- Average

4. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The entrepreneurship was first established. In the 1700 and he mining has evolved the entrepreneurship is very an old concept according to which anyone who runs business is called an entrepreneur. Economic growth hinges upon entrepreneurship. A vibrant entrepreneurial climate. Provides new jobs. Increase assess competitive and produces novel goods and services. The economic development of advance country of the world has been attributed to the growth of entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship can be described as a process of action an entrepreneur. Undertakes to establish his enterprise. Entrepreneurship is a creative activity. It is the ability to create and build something from practically nothing. It is a knack of sensing opportunity where others see chaos, contradiction and confusion. Entrepreneurship is the attitude of Mind to seek opportunities, take calculated risks and derive benefits by setting up a venture. It comprises of numerous activities involved in conception, creation and running an enterprise.

Entrepreneurship can be described as a process of action an entrepreneur Undertakes to establish his enterprise. Entrepreneurship is a creative activity. It is the ability to create and build something from practically nothing. It is a knack of sensing opportunity where others see chaos, contradiction and confusion. Entrepreneurship is the attitude of Mind to seek opportunities, take calculated risks and derive benefits by setting up a venture. It comprises of numerous activities involved in conception, creation and running an enterprise.

PART –TRAINING INSTRUCTION:-

Entrepreneurship has been considered the backbone of economic development. It has been well established that the level of economic growth of a region to a large extent, depends on the level of entrepreneurial activities in the region. The myth that entrepreneurs are born, no more holds good, rather it is well recognized now that the entrepreneurs can be created and nurtured through appropriate interventions in the form of entrepreneurship development programmes.

In the era of liberalization, privatization and globalization along with ongoing IT revolution, capable entrepreneurs are making use of the opportunities emerging from the evolving scenario. However, a large segment of the population, particularly in the industrially backward regions/rural areas generally lags behind in taking advantage of these opportunities. Therefore, there is a need to provide skill development and entrepreneurship development training to such people in order to mainstream them in the ongoing process of economic growth.

Entrepreneurship development and training is, thus, one of the key elements for development of micro and small enterprises (MSEs), particularly, the first generation entrepreneurs. To undertake this task on regular basis, the Ministry has set up three national-level Entrepreneurship Development Institutes (EDIs).

These are the National Institute for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (NI-MSME), Hyderabad;

The Indian Institute of Entrepreneurship (IIE),

Guwahati and the National Institute for Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development (NIESBUD), Noida.

Further, the Ministry has been implementing (in addition to the schemes of MSME-DO) an important scheme, namely, Scheme for Assistance for Strengthening of Training Infrastructure of Existing and New Entrepreneurship Development Institutes (EDIs). The main objectives of the scheme are

1. promoting entrepreneurship for creating self-employment through enterprise creation;
2. (ii) facilitating creation of training infrastructure; and
3. (iii) Supporting research on entrepreneurship related issues.

Rural self Employment Training Institutes (RSETIs):-

Encouraged by the hugely successful RUDSETI (Rural Development and Self Employment Training Institute) model initiated in 1982 in Ujire, Karnataka, for promoting entrepreneurship amongst rural youth, the Government of India decided to replicate the model across the country in 2008-09 by establishing one Rural Self Employment Training Institute (RSETI) in each district of the country in partnership with banks and the State Government. Before the launch of the scheme, some 122 institutes were already being run by the banks under their own initiative. The Government of India approved an amount of Rs.500 crore for the remaining districts so that each district has one RSETI for training the rural youth to take up self employment as a livelihood option.

TRAINING PHASE:-

Entrepreneurship development programmes, as pointed out earlier, conducted by different organizations. Even then, most of the inputs imparted are more or less the same. Some of the major inputs provided are:

- **Behavioral inputs:** Achievement motivation training, communication skills, problem solving skills, interpersonal skills, creativity, decision making, etc..
- **Inputs to facilitate decision making process to set up a new venture:** Business opportunity guidance, information, project planning and technical inputs.
- **Managerial inputs:** office administration, finance, accounting, project management, project report preparation and similar management inputs etc.
- **Technical inputs:** On the job training in the particular product line so that the entrepreneur knows the intricacies of the production process.

Training programmers:-

Training is one of the significant aspects of the organization. The institute conducts variety of training programmes for the entrepreneurs in the areas of marketing, exports, packaging etc.

Quality/ Technical up gradation

The institute undertakes number of measures to promote quality and technical up gradation. Technical experts from the organization discuss the future of the manufactured products with new and established entrepreneurs.

Training facilities

SIDO arranges various training programmes according to the needs of the entrepreneurs. It has sufficient infrastructure to provide for these training programmers.

Small Scale Industries Board (SSI Board)

The Small Scale Industries Board is the apex advisory body constituted to render advice to the government on all matters related to small scale sector. The range of development work in the small scale sector includes various departments/ ministries and several agencies of Central/ State Governments.

Small Industries Service Institutes (SISIs) the Small Industries Service Institutes are set up. To provide consultancy and training to small entrepreneurs.

The main functions of SISI are:

- To serve as interface between State and Central Governments.
- To provide technical support services.
- To conduct entrepreneurship development programmes
- To initiate promotional programmes.

NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT (NIESBUD), NOIDA, UP.

The National Institute for Entrepreneurship & Small Business Development (NIESBUD) is an autonomous Institute established in 1983 under the administrative control of M/o MSME. The major areas of intervention of the Institute are conducting of Training Programmes, Research/ Review/Evaluation Activities, Publications & Training Aids, Cluster Development Activities, Garment Incubation-cum-Training Centre, Intellectual Property Facilitation Centre, Employment Generation/Assistance, Hand-Holding Assistance for Enterprise Creation, Consultancy Services (National and International) etc.

The activities of the Institute have witnessed a quantum jump in the recent past.

From 355 training programmes during 2009- 10, the number increased to 3,886 during

2013-14, a growth of nearly 1100%. Similarly, the revenue generation also increased from Rs. 444.36 lakh to Rs. 4,200 lakh during the period, signifying about 10 fold increases.

PERFORMANCE OF NIESBUD DURING 2012-13 AND DURING 2013-14

	Category of the Programme	2012-13 2013-14			
		No of Progs	No of Progs	No of Progs	No of Progs
1	TTPs/ Ps/Conferences /Workshops	56	1.043	132	824
2	ToTs / EDPs /ESDPs-ATI	1,929	49.269	1500	39.979
3	EDPs / ESDPs – Non-ATI	132	2.241	56	505
4	International Programmes	12	245	13	252
	Total	2.129	53.953	3886	99560

This achievement of training 99,560 beneficiaries during the year 2013-14 is against 53,953 beneficiaries trained by the Institute during the year 2012-13.

Institutional Support for Entrepreneurship Development

S/no	Name of Institute	Place	Activities
01	National Institute of Small Industry Extension and Training (NISJET)	Hyderabad	Training, research and consultancy services
02	Indian Institute of Entrepreneurship	Guwahati	Training, research and consultancy services
03	National Institute of Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development (NIESBUD)	New Delhi	Coordinating and overseeing activities of various institutes /agencies engaged in entrepreneurship development
04	Integrated Training Centre (Industries)	Nilokheri	Conducts EDP course
05	Institute for Design of Electrical Measuring Instruments (IDEMI)	Mumbai	Render services to the instrumentation industry
06	Central Institute of Hand Tools	Jalandhar	Aims at rapid growth of the hand tool sector
07	Hand Tool Design Development and Training Centre	Nagaur	Assistance for improvement in productivity, betterment in quality, high value addition
08	Central Tool Room	Ludhiana	Provides services in the area of consultancy, tool design and manufacture and technical training
09	Central Tool Room and Training Centre	Kolkata	Training, design and manufacture of complicated precision tools for the telecom industry and other common facility services
10	Central Institute of Tool Design (CITD)	Hyderabad	Training,CAD/CAM centre to train post-graduate trainees, automatic process control unit, and so on
11	Product-cum-Process Development Centre for Sports Goods	Meerut	Training, process and product development of sports goods, R & D
12	Product-cum-Process Development Centre for Essential Oils	Kannauj	Modernise and upgrade technology status for the essential oils and perfumery industry
13	Product-cum-Process Development Centre	Agra	Provide better technology to small-scale foundry and forging units, process and product development, and provision of design for melting equipment, testing facilities
14	Electronic Service and Training Centre	Ramnagar	Training, technical and consultancy services
15	Centre for the improvement of Glass industry	Firozabad	adoption of new technologies and products
16	National Small Industries Corporation	New Delhi	Supply of machinery, marketing assistance, training

Part-B Finance instructions:-

Entrepreneurs shape economic destiny of nations by creating wealth and employment, offering products and services, and generating taxes for governments. That is why entrepreneurship has closely been linked to economic growth in the literature on the subject. Entrepreneurs convert ideas into economic opportunities through innovations which are considered to be

major source of competitiveness in an increasingly globalizing world economy. Therefore, most governments in the world strive to augment supply of competent and globally competitive entrepreneurs in their respective countries. While developed nations have a reasonably good pace of entrepreneurial supply, most developing countries suffer from dearth of such entrepreneurs. This is one of the reasons for the poverty in developing countries, despite their rich resource endowments.

Financial schemes for women entrepreneurship: With a view that women entrepreneurs should come forward in industrial field and become self-sufficient, governmental and financial institutions have announced many schemes of providing financial assistance. Seed Capital Scheme- In order to start one's own business this scheme is undertaken by the government. Mohanty (2004) suggested that various self-employment and income generating schemes such as IRDP, SEEU, PMRY, SSI, KVI and DWCRA implemented in Orissa have made significant contribution towards economic empowerment and self-employment of women and development of women entrepreneurship.

Financing institutions:-

Finance is one of the essential requirements of an enterprise. Without adequate funds, no business can be developed. In India, Central and state governments are promoting number of financial institutions to bring in the industrial development in the country. Some of the important financial institutions are:

1. Industrial development bank of India (IDBI)
2. National bank for agriculture and rural development (NABARD)
3. Export import bank of India
4. Small industrial development bank of India (SIDBI)
5. Industrial investment bank of India
6. Industrial finance corporation of India (IFCI)
7. Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India (ICICI)
8. Industrial Reconstruction Bank of India
9. Indian banking system and commercial banks
10. State Financial Corporations
11. Life Insurance corporation of India (LIC)
12. Unit Trust of India (UTI)

1) Industrial development bank of India (IDBI)

IDBI is the apex institution in the field of industrial finance. It was established under the IDBI act 1964 as a wholly owned subsidiary of Reserve bank of India. It started its operations from 1st July 1964. It was de-associated from RBI under Public Financial Institution Laws (Amendment) Act 1976 and restructured as the principal financial institution of the country with the following objectives. Create a principal institution for long term finance Coordinate the institutions. Working in the field for planned development of industrial sector Provide technical and administrative support to the industries. And to conduct research and development activities for the benefit of industrial sector.

IDBI provides long term finance to industrial sector. It is engaged in direct financing of the industrial activities as well as refinance and rediscounting of bills against finance made available by commercial banks under their various schemes for industrial development purposes.

IDBI is the tenth largest bank in the world in terms of development. Some of the institutions which have been built by IDBI are:

- The National Stock Exchange (NSE),
- National Securities Depository Services Ltd.
- Stock Holding Corporation of India Ltd.
- Entrepreneurship Development Institute:-

Since entrepreneurship development is the precondition to industrial development, IDBI played a major role in setting up of the Entrepreneurship Development Institute of India for promoting entrepreneurship in the country. IDBI also provides financial support to various organizations in conducting studies and surveys beneficial for industrial development.

2) National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD):-

NABARD is one of the apex development banks. It came into existence on July 12, 1982 under NABARD ACT, 1981 with a capital of Rs. 100crore contributed by Central Government and RBI, with its main office in Mumbai. The set up has been created by merging Agriculture Credit Department and Rural Planning and Credit Cell of RBI and took over the entire functions of Agriculture Refinance and Development Corporation.

NABARD raises funds through National Rural Credit-Long Term operations, National Rural Credit Establishment Fund, bonds and debentures guaranteed by Central Government, borrowing from RBI, Central Government or any other organization approved by Central Government and funds from external sources. Its developmental functions are co-ordination of various institutions, acting as agent of Government and RBI and providing training and research facilities.

The regulatory functions include inspection of Regional Rural Banks, and Cooperative Banks, receipt of returns and making of recommendations for opening new branches.

3) Export Import Bank of India (EXIM BANK)

It is apex institution for coordinating the working of institutions engaged in financing exports and import of goods and services. With initial authorized capital of Rs. 200 corer, Exim Bank was established on Jan 01, 1982 under Export Import Bank of India Act 1982, which took over the export finance activities of IDBI. It raises funds by way of bonds and debentures, borrowing from RBI or other institutions, raising foreign deposits.

It undertakes following types of functions;

- Direct finance to exporter of goods.
- Direct finance to software exports and consultancy services.
- Finance for overseas joint ventures and turnkey construction project.
- Finance for import and export of machinery and equipment on lease basis.
- Finance for deferred payment facility.
- Issue of guarantees.
- Multi-currency financing facility to project exporters.
- Export bills rediscounting.
- Refinance to commercial banks in India.
- Guaranteeing the obligations.

4) Small Industries Development Bank of India SIDBI

Was established under SIDBI Act 1988 and commenced its operations with effect from April 02, 1990, as a subsidiary of IDBI. It took over the IDBI business relating to small scale industries including National Equity Scheme and Small Industries Development Fund. The objective of establishment of SIDBI is to strengthen and broad base the existing institutional arrangement to meet the requirements of small scale industries and tiny industries.

Some of its functions include:

- Providing working capital through single window scheme
- Providing refinance support to banks/development finance institutions.
- Undertaking direct financing of SSI units.

5) Industrial Investment Bank of India IIBI

Was established as Industrial Reconstruction Corporation Limited during 1971 when it was renamed as Industrial Reconstruction Bank of India with effect from March 20, 1985 under IRBI Act 1984, to take over the function of industrial reconstruction corporation. During 1997, the bank was converted into a joint stock company by naming it as Industrial Investment Bank of India.

6) Industrial Finance Corporation of India IFCI

Was established under IFCI Act during July 1948 as India's first development bank. The main objectives, for which IFCI was established, are to make medium and long term credit available to the industrial undertakings and to assist them in creation of industrial facilities.

Its functions include:

- Subscription and underwriting of public issues of shares and debentures.
- Guaranteeing of foreign currency loans and also deferred payment
- Guarantees Merchant banking, leasing and equipment finance
- During 1994, IFCI was converted into a joint stock

7) Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India ICICI

was set up during 1955 as a private company with a view to provide support to industrial sector in India by way of rupee and foreign currency loans, particularly the private international investment and World Bank funds, to assist the industry in private sector. Its functions include:

- Subscription and underwriting of capital issues
- Guaranteeing the payment for credits
- Merchant banking, equipment leasing and project counseling.

8) Industrial Reconstruction Bank of India

Government of India set up the Industrial Reconstruction Corporation of India in April 1971 under the Indian Companies Act mainly to look after the special problems of sick units and provide assistance for their speedy reconstruction and rehabilitation(Khanka,1999:116) In August 1984 Industrial Reconstruction Corporation of India was converted into Industrial Reconstruction Bank of India(IRBI).IRBI has to work as the principal all India credit and reconstruction agency for industrial revival, assisting and promoting industrial development and rehabilitation of industrial concerns.

9) Indian Banking System and Commercial Banks

Indian banking system comprises of Reserve bank of India and other banking institutions like NABARD, National Housing Bank, Export Import Bank of India, Commercial banks (public sector banks, private sector banks, and foreign banks)Regional Rural banks, Co-operative banks, Development financial institutions such as IDBI, ICICI, IFCI, and other financial intermediaries (LIC, GIC, UTI)

Commercial banks in the context of entrepreneurship development

Commercial banks came into the business of supporting small scale industries in a significant way only after the nationalization of banks in 1969. Till that time these banks were financing small scale industries. RBI advised commercial banks to initiate activities of increase credit flow to the small scale industries. Different schemes implemented by different banks are as follows: State Bank of India launched entrepreneurship development programme in 1978.

This programme was of one month duration, having three phases. Initiation phase: creating awareness about entrepreneurial opportunities. Development phase:

Training in developing motivation and managerial skills Support phase: Counseling, encouragement and infrastructural support for establishing and running enterprises.

State Bank of India (SBI) implemented scheme of financial assistance to technically qualified or trained entrepreneurs.

Bank of India is operating following schemes for entrepreneurship development in the country.

- A. Star artisan credit card scheme.
- B. Small entrepreneur credit card scheme
- C. Star SSI supreme scheme
- D. Small entrepreneur trade card scheme
- E. Star self-employment credit card scheme

f) Scheme for employment enhancement and poverty eradication.

Punjab National Bank through its Merchant Banking division provides number of benefits to small and middle level entrepreneurs.

Punjab National Bank initiated a “MahilaUdyamNidhi Scheme” for women entrepreneurs.

10) State Financial Corporation (SFC)

Financial Corporation Act 1951, made it mandatory that every state in India will have its own established financial corporation. The main function of State Financial Corporation is to provide mainly the term loan assistance to small and medium scale industries for acquiring fixed assets like land, building, plant and machinery.

SFCs undertake the issue of stock, shares, bonds or debentures of industrial concerns and to grant loans and advances to industrial concerns repayable within a period not exceeding 20 years.

11) Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC)

Life Insurance Corporation of India was established under the LIC Act in 1956 as a wholly owned corporation of the Government of India. LIC has been deploying its funds according to plan priorities. LIC also provides term loans and underwriting/ direct subscription to shares and debentures of corporate sector.

+ Promotional Institutions

Government at state and central level has introduced lot of measures to support the growth and development of entrepreneurs. Government has set up number of promoting agencies and institutions to help emerging and established entrepreneurs, especially small and medium entrepreneurs. These institutions support the entrepreneurs in respect of training, finance and marketing. Some of such institutions are:

1. District Industries centers (DICs)
2. Small Industries Development Organization (SIDO)
3. The National Small Industries Corporation Ltd.(NSIC)
4. Small Scale Industries Board (SSIB)
5. Small industries Service Institutes (SISIs)
6. Industrial estates.

+ Supporting of other financial institutions:-

Promotional Institutions Government at state and central level has introduced lot of measures to support the growth and development of entrepreneurs. Government has set up number of promoting agencies and institutions to help emerging and established entrepreneurs, especially small and medium entrepreneurs. These institutions support the entrepreneurs in respect of training, finance and marketing. Some of such institutions are:

1. District Industries centers (DICs)
2. Small Industries Development Organization(SIDO)
3. The National Small Industries Corporation Ltd.(NSIC)
4. Small Scale Industries Board (SSIB)
5. Small industries Service Institutes (SISIs)
6. Industrial estates
7. Khadi and Village Industries Corporation (KVIC)
8. Technical Consultancy Organizations,

Support from Family Members, Friends and Relatives Family members including spouse, children and parents create a strong support system for the budding entrepreneurs. This support can be emotional, financial, administrative or technical. Any businessperson has to face various problems like ups and downs in the business, payment recovery problem and

financial crunch resulting from it, worker’s non-co-operation and industrial unrest. Spouse can extend support during all such types of crises. In some communities like Marwari, there is a provision of community funds which can be used to help the needy entrepreneurs.

Table 4.1: Growth Dimensions of Small Scale Industries in Karnataka

Year	No of Regd. SSI Units	Investment (In Lakhs)	Employment (In Nos)
1980-81	2776	3042	21357
1981-82	3396	4954	29214
1982-83	6096	2794	31420
1983-84	7479	6397	36314
1984-85	8073	6324	55849
1985-86	11634	8787	60796
1986-87	11179	9409	56888
1987-88	10530	10165	52498
1988-89	9811	10533	50448
1989-90	9700	11247	51521
1990-91	9884	11843	53568
1991-92	10588	18623	61903
1992-93	11368	19773	62835
1993-94	12614	19891	69563
1994-95	13503	26463	73999
1995-96	11856	33160	70903
1996-97	13529	35811	67631
1997-98	34402	66451	132978
1998-99	13422	59752	69579
1999-00	15938	73706	88279
2000-01	16554	65158	85792
2001-02	16964	47883	73195
2002-03	12029	40836	57371
2003-04	12220	37054	56790
2004-05	11238	38541	49998
2005-06	12780	43647	58133
2006-07	12580	46542	57517

Source: Government of Karnataka, DIC (District Industries Centre,

The numbers of registered SSI units have increased at a fast rate during the last three decades. The total number of registered SSI units rose by almost three times from 2776 in 1980-81 to 8073 in 1984-85 – a period of five years. The growth in the subsequent 5 years has indicated a slow and fluctuating trend from 8073 in 1984-85 to 9700 in 1989-90. The growth rate is sustained and continuous and the total number of registered SSI units rose to 13503 in 1994-95 and further to 15938 in 1999-2000. With a small increase of 16554 units in 2000-01 the total number of SSI units declined to 12580 in 2006-07. – A period of five years. The growth in the subsequent 5 years has indicated a slow and fluctuating trend from 8073 in 1984-85 to 9700 in 1989-90. The growth rate is sustained and continuous and the total number of registered SSI units rose to 13503 in 1994-95 and further to 15938 in 1999-2000. With a small increase of 16554 units in 2000-01 the total number of SSI units declined to 12580 in 2006-07.

Table 4.2: Orientation and plans of SMEs

Orientation and plans of SMEs in times of crisis	The same workload	Reduced workload	Closing the business	Transfer business to others
Business expansion	55,6%	6,1%	4,7%	1,5%
32,2%	47,2%	3,8%	2,0%	1,1%
45,9%	37,6%	2,4%	0,9%	0,5%
58,7%	59,1%	4,6%	5,3%	2,0%
29,1%	48,5%	3,8%	2,9%	1,2%
43,6%				

Table 4.3: OUTSTANDING BANK CREDIT TO MICRO AND SMALL ENTERPRISES

As on last reporting Friday of March	Public Sector Banks	Private Sector Banks	Foreign Banks	All Scheduled Commercial Banks
2005	67.800	8592	6907	83498
2006	82.434 (21.6)	10.421 (21.3)	8.430 (22.1)	1,01,285 (21.3)
2007	1,02,550 (24.4)	13,136 (26.1)	11,637 (38.0)	1,27,323 (25.7)
2008	1,51,137 (47.4)	46,912 (257.1)	15,489 (33.1)	2,13,538 (67.7)
2009	1,91,408 (26.6)	46,656 (0.0)	18,063 (16.6)	2,56,127 (19.9)
2010	2,78,398 (45.4)	64,534 (38.3)	21,069 (16.6)	3,64,001 (42.1)
2011	3,76,625 (35.3)	87,857 (36.1)	21,535 (2,2)	4,86,017 (33.5)
2012	3,96,343 (5.24)	1,10,514 (25.79)	(21,760) (1.05)	(5,28,617) (8.77)
2012 (Provisional)	5,00,250 (26.22)	(1,52,554) (38.04)	(31,993) (47.03)	6,84,797 (29.55)

Source: Reserve Bank of India

Registration of Small Scale Industrial Units in Karnataka

Registration of Small Scale Industrial Units in Karnataka (1994-1995 to 2008-2009)			
Item	No of SSI Units Set Up	Investment (Rs. in Lakh)	Employment (' 000)
1994-95	163454	193616	1077
1995-96	175310	226776	1148
1996-97	188839	262587	1216
1997-98	223241	329038	1349
1998-99	236663	388790	1419
1999-00	252601	462496	1507
2000-01	269155	527654	1593
2001-02	286119	575538	1666
2002-03	298148	616374	1723
2003-04	310368	653428	1780
2004-05	32160	691969	1830
2005-06	334386	735616	1888
2006-07	346966	782158	1946
2007-08	361950	894817	2069
2008-09	377655	996434	107103

Source: Planning, Programme Monitoring and Statistics Department, Govt. of Karnataka. (10573), (12042)

Entrepreneurship development in today SSI contribution is very high and one more numbers of industry day by day increges in Karnataka 1994-95 year numbers unites /industries 163454 SSI investment 193616 and ant that employment of industries in Karnataka has been 1077. And at aame time 2001-02 ear in industries in Karnataka SSI investment of 220776 and at same time in employment of 1666 of employment and 2008-09 numbers of industries in Karnataka 377655 and SSI investment of the 996434 of investment and employment of Karnataka 107103.

Industrial Approvals in Karnataka

Industrial Approvals in Karnataka (1994-1995 to 2008-2009)		
Item	Letter Internet Issued	of Industrial Licences Issued
1994-95	22	10
1995-96	10	2
1996-97	51	6
1997-98	14	4
1998-99	8	3
1999-00	7	3
2000-01	21	7
2001-02	5	2
2002-03	4	3
2003-04	3	4
2004-05	-	-
2005-06	-	-
2006-07	9	-
2007-08	10	-
2008-09	12	-

Source: Planning, Programme Monitoring and Statistics Department, Govt.of Karnataka. (10573), (12042)

SSI in Karnataka has been 1994-95 in letter internet issued in industries 22 and industries licenses in 10 and because restrictions of govt scheme and more problem of location and more training problem in Karnataka and last 2008-09 lettere issue in Karnataka 12

5. FINDING AND SUGGESTION

Finding:-

1. Entrepreneurship development programs 2012-13 NI-MSME as apex intuitions has been 2012-13 in 1603 to and 2013-14 in 23670 and more.
2. Other Programmers Ms-MSME 2014 And EntrupriniinurshipInstructionalProgram’sInplimantatoby 54.
3. Entrepreneurship development programs EDPs establish by 2013-14 in 24to 710.
4. Management development progremmes MDPs establish by 2013-14 to 27 to 943 the last year total last before year total programs in 2013-14 510 to 23359
5. Lest catogary of the 2014th international program’s total 99560.
6. Groth small scale industries in Karnataka in darning the 2000-01 and small scale industries in Karnataka financial supports in investment in 65158.
7. At same 2006-07 numbers of small scale industries 12580 the year dicreges industries because lack of financial supports.
8. The outstanding bank credit to micro and small industries public sector bank lone issues that 2012th5.00.250 .
9. Forigen bank lone provides by micro and small industries lone 31.993
- 10.Karnataka CEDOOK number of program’s trained in 43806.
- 11.Restratoin of small industries unites in Karnataka 2008-09 in 3.77.655 unites.
- 12.Industries approach in karanataka level of internet insued in 2008-09. 12.
- 13.Classification industries has been Rs 50 million US\$ 1 Million.

Suggestions:-

- There should be a continuous attempt to inspire, encourage, motivate and co-operate women entrepreneurs.
- There is need in attempting to establish proper training institutes for enhancing their level of work-knowledge, skills, risk-taking abilities, enhancing their capabilities.
- Establishing various policies to offer easy finance schemes for economically strengthening the position of Entrepreneurship.

Suggestion for improvement of the Entrepreneurship Development Programme

- EDP helped to expand the activity confidently, interview with successful entrepreneurs, panel discussion with other entrepreneurs will help.
- Requires need based skill training by extending the duration of the training.
- EDP helped to gain self confidence. Helped to gain social status and Earning increased by adopting managerial skills.
- For rural women and man it has helped and made them to understand Government schemes.
- EDP has helped to aware of developmental schemes.
- Training must be conducted in the nearby place, specific skill training will help more , with this training gained confidence, helped to financial problem and to develop
- Teaching method must be improved.
- The duration of the training must be increased.
- Needs more skill training, which will help in the long run.
- Number of days is less, needs more days, field visit must be included. Programme helped to lead an independent life.

6. CONCLUSION

Entrepreneurship has been considered the back bone of economic development entrepreneurship is a creative activity it is the ability to created and build something from practically nothing it is a knack of sensing opportunity. Where others see chaos, contradiction and confusion entrepreneurship to seek opportunities entrepreneurship can be development of nation is the created own new jobs entrepreneurship is the most of the impartantschemeand income generating of the country. Entrepreneurshipand institutional support of the development of the country. Institutional support of the that the increasing of the income of the nation and developing of the country that have been finding of the study as concern of the institutional supported as entrepreneurship economic destiny of the nation by creating the jobs and many other financial institutions supporting the enterprneuship for exampal IDBI, IFCI, LIC, NABARD, UTI. All the financial institutional supporting the enterpreneuship government of Karnataka implimanting of the many schemes of the enterpreneuship of the financial assessment of the financial institution.

Financial Assistance to Small and Medium scale Enterprises plays a vital role because Small and Medium scale Enterprises have been considered as the engine of Economic growth. It encourages the new entrepreneurs by providing them the loans and helping their dreams to be alive and come true.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Books:-

- [1] Dr. M. V. Raghavalu, Associate Professor, Department of PG studies in Economics,
- [2] SSA. Government First Grade College, Bellary-583101, Karnataka State.
- [3] Chapter 1 "Entrepreneurship Development in India".
- [4] Chapter 3 employments.
- [5] Chapter 3 Institutional Supports forEntrepreneurship Development
- [6] Chapter 4 training Entrepreneurship Development (Annual Report 2007-2008)

- [7] Chapter 7 Intuitional support (Management and Entrepreneurship)
- [8] Sponsored by the Ministry of MSME, Government of India New Delhi

References:-

- [9] R.Ravi, Dr. Avinash Roy: (2014) A Study on Effects of Micro Financing on MSMEs in Karnataka,
- [10] Bhagyalaxmi and Dr. Ishwara. (2014) Dual Responsibility of Rural Women Entrepreneurs – Issues and Challenges.
- [11] Laxmi B. Parab and R. L. Hyderabad, (2014) State and Institutional Support for Women Entrepreneurship Development: A study of Dharwad District in Karnataka State.
- [12] Dr. M.V.Raghavalu. (2011), Role of Institutional Agencies for the development of Women Entrepreneurs in Karnataka.
- [13] Prof. Dr. B. R. Kamble, (2001) Contribution of financial instruction in promoting women entrepreneurs.
- [14] Dr. S. Mohan & Mrs. R. Revathi (2012) Impact of Training on Entrepreneurial Development.
- [15] BABA, G.K (2013) the Challenges of Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria.
- [16] Bharathi V. Sunagara and Megha Jigalurb, (2013) Critical Issues of Women Entrepreneurship with Special reference to specific business units in North Karnataka.
- [17] Dr Sharanappasaidapur&ngithasaidapur (2012): Women candle entrepreneurs in Gulbarga district.
- [18] Asharani S and Dr. K. E Sriramappa “Women Entrepreneurship in Karnataka”2014
- [19] Ms. INDIRA KUMARI “A Study on Entrepreneurship Development Process in India” 2014

Website:-

- [20] Website: World Bank Report 2010 – 11.
- [21] Website: CMIE Report 2011.
- [22] Website: Karnataka.nic.in.
- [23] Website: www.msme.gov.in
- [24] Source: Government of Karnataka, DIC (District Industries Centre),
- [25] Www. Karnataka's Population 2015
- [26] Source: Annual Report 2013-14 MSME.
- [27] Economic Surveys-India and Karnataka.
- [28] Website: www.nimsme.org